

**The Report of the 2004 Science and Management Audit of
the NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science**

**Science and Management Audit Report for the NERC Centres for Atmospheric
Science**

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13 to 15 September 2004

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Science

Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)

**Science and Management Audit of the NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science
(NCAS)**

Background to the Review

1. A Science and Management Audit (SMA) is an external and independent evaluation of scientific and management performance of a Research or Collaborative Centre funded by NERC. It provides an assurance for the NERC Accounting Officer (i.e. Chief Executive) and for Council that the science or service is managed well. The SMA Team membership for NCAS was independent of NERC.
2. NCAS is one of the NERC Collaborative Centres, with its activities delivered by universities (and analogues) under contract to NERC. Staff are employed by the host university. NCAS was established on 1 April 2002, as a requirement of the Government Spending Review 2000, and funded until 31 March 2006 (NCAS I). As a Collaborative Centre, NCAS provides a directed programme of research and services/facilities, to maintain long-term capability in a strategically important area of NERC science.
3. There are seven centres that carry out the research and technology programmes within NCAS:
 - Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit (ACMSU) -
 - Chemistry-climate interactions,
 - British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) –
 - Data services,
 - Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling (CGAM) -
 - Climate variability and change,
 - Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition (DIAC) –
 - Atmospheric composition,
 - Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM) –
 - Aircraft facility,
 - Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement (UFAM) –
 - Specialized measurement instruments,
 - Universities' Weather Research Network (UWERN) –
 - Small-scale processes and weather.

The Team visited two of the centres of NCAS but before doing so it considered papers prepared by NCAS and the NERC Evaluation Team (who managed the review process on behalf of NERC). The conclusions have been drawn from both the papers prepared and the interviews held with staff during the site visits.

4. The respective Directors and Heads of the Centres are:

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- NCAS - Professor Alan Thorpe,
 - ACMSU – Professor John Pyle FRS,
 - BADC – Dr Bryan Lawrence
 - CGAM – Professor Julia Slingo,
 - DIAC – Professor Mike Pilling,
 - FAAM – Dr John Foot (acting),
 - UFAM – Dr Alan Blyth
 - UWERN – Professor Paul Mason FRS
5. Of these seven research facilities the following four were reviewed in full: – CGAM, ACMSU, UWERN and BADC. Previous SMAs have been carried out for BADC in 2000 and CGAM and ACMSU in 2001. The remaining three - DIAC, UFAM and FAAM – provided progress reports as they have only recently been initiated.
 6. The Terms of Reference for the NCAS SMA are found at Annex 1. The membership list can be found at Annex 2. The timetable for the visit is at Annex 3. An organisation diagram showing the relationship within NCAS and indicating the funding weighting is at Annex 4.
 7. The SMA Team will deliver its report to the Chief Executive. The NCAS Director, in consultation with the Chief Executive must then implement the recommendations and provide a progress report eighteen months after the review. This update will be reviewed by the NERC Evaluation Team, which is responsible for checking whether or not the key SMA/Review recommendations have been carried out, before submitting the progress update, with its observations, to the Chief Executive.

The Mission of the NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)

8. The mission of NCAS is to provide leadership and act as the focus for atmospheric science research in the UK, to enhance the effective delivery by the academic community of excellent research for the benefit of UK society. Its objective is to increase scientific knowledge of the atmosphere and of its role in the Earth system, including improved prediction of global and regional change. It seeks to achieve its mission and objective by application of the following criteria:-

- Maintaining long-term expertise in critical areas of atmospheric science – by distributing expertise across academic departments,
- Conducting World-leading research on key scientific challenges,
- Providing services and facilities for the wider atmospheric science community,
- Facilitating and enhancing collaboration in research that can only be carried out through collaboration between different research groups and across disciplines,
- Seeking to be as inclusive as possible (*via* a broad network),
- Providing advice to government and other stakeholders,
- Acting as a catalyst for winning other funding.

9. NCAS sees its significant science and technology challenges as:

- Quantifying global, regional and local changes to atmospheric composition and increasing knowledge of the interaction of atmospheric composition with weather, climate and the biosphere,
- Increasing the knowledge of the physics and dynamics of the atmosphere so as to enable their accurate representation in climate and weather forecasting models, and developing environmental prediction applications such as air quality,
- Increasing the knowledge of climate variability and change on timescales of weeks to millennia, developing the capability to perform comprehensive simulations of the earth system on these timescales, and establishing the utility and skill of climate change predictions at the regional scale,
- Developing further the fundamental laboratory studies and underpinning technologies for observing and modelling the atmosphere, necessary to carry out both laboratory and field-based atmospheric science research.

Executive Summary

10. The SMA Team noted that the Collaborative Centres model for funding directed research is a recent innovation for NERC. The Team's overall impression was that NCAS is proving successful in applying the model to achieve significant enhancements in collaborative research and output in this scientifically varied field, both within and between the communities of the four Centres under review. This success is due mostly to the excellent leadership shown by the Director and the individual heads of Centres and Facilities. In the short history of NCAS the organisation has established a coherent identity offering NERC excellent value for money through the management of the research communities and through the use of existing university employees and buildings. The Team considered that NCAS exercises impressive leverage in obtaining external funding.
11. The science conducted in NCAS is overall of high quality, with several components conducting world-leading research. In particular, of the three Centres whose science was assessed, two were placed in the $\alpha 5$ category (outstanding) and one was placed in the $\alpha 4$ (excellent) category.
12. NCAS fulfils its remit as an important national capability. The Director can now turn his attention to improving communications with Government and other potential and actual users.
13. The SMA Team examined the status of the NCAS mission within the overall NERC strategy and concluded that the contribution of atmospheric science to understanding climate change was so important that the work of NCAS should command additional financial and infrastructure support. The Team also considered that much of the work of the NCAS Centres was at the forefront of chemical and geo-physical Earth System Science, particularly as it pertains to integrative modelling, and that this experience should be fully recognised in deploying an Earth System Science approach across the NERC research agenda. The work of the various centres of NCAS that were not subject to a full review in this SMA was commended, with a concern that several centres may find their work commitments, which are essential to NCAS strategy, could not be supported at current funding levels.
14. Staff within NCAS had a very positive approach to their work. There remain problems with staff working on contracts rather than permanent employment and support staff who may have different career paths from academically employed personnel. These problems, common to many NERC funded science activities, pose significant risks to the achievement of NCAS' objectives. The SMA team welcomed the fact that discussions on these problems were ongoing with the Director of People, Skills and Communication at NERC.
15. The provision of data, instruments and aircraft was recognised as being in line with the science conducted by the research centres. The Data Centre was assessed as managing its services and facilities in an excellent ($\alpha 4$) manner. There were issues of prioritisation concerned with super-computing facilities

government. Senior NCAS staff are members of the Department of the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) Boards, of the Global Climate Observing System Committees, of several supercomputing Committees, of Met Office Advisory Committees, of Royal Society Committees and various assessments for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Mike Pilling is a member of the review panel for the third Heathrow runway and a recent prominent press report, from the British Association for the Advancement of Science meeting, quoted him as “a Government air quality adviser” when discussing clean air quality.

22. The SMA team noted the speech by the Prime Minister, giving the Prince of Wales Business and the Environment Programme tenth anniversary lecture in Whitehall on 15 September, when he said climate change would be a priority issue during his presidency of G8 in the latter half of next year. The team noted that the PM’s views were in line with NCAS’ aims and that NCAS was well placed to offer the scientific and technological research and advice required by government.
23. Notwithstanding the complexity and number of established advice links, the **SMA Team felt that the connection between NCAS and Government and other users could be even further strengthened.** CGAM’s links with the Meteorological Office’s Hadley Centre were welcomed (Hadley Centre Climate Models Partners Board) and the team felt that these links should continue to be developed. The Hadley Centre should be encouraged to take the lead on climate change, whereas NCAS should take a similar role on climate variability.
24. For all the NCAS centres an existing and appropriate conduit into government and the atmospheric user community in general is the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology (FAST) **although in its current guise FAST is not operating to its best potential.** The SMA team considers that some effort should be put into re-invigorating FAST to make it a more effective working link, fostering active involvement in NCAS research strategy and giving a higher profile public face to the work of NCAS.
25. Determining and establishing effective mechanisms for providing advice to government and other public bodies is a problem shared with other NERC Centres. The SMA team felt that there would be mutual benefit in NCAS working with, in particular, the Tyndall Centre and the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (CEH) to improve the recognition and use of NERC Centres as sources of information and advice.

Term of Reference 2

To assess the effectiveness of the scientific and management leadership and process for cultivating long-term vision/mission and strategy, and the contribution of NCAS towards NERC’s Mission and 5-year Strategy. QQR 3.11 iv

26. NCAS is financially managed through a series of contracts administered through NERC on behalf of the Director, NCAS. The Director of NCAS provides the overall scientific and administrative leadership for the seven

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centres including financial allocations within NCAS, managing the interaction between the Centres and with the wider scientific community, scientific strategy development and the relationship with the Swindon Office. The Director of NCAS has his salary and that of his secretary paid by NERC, together with overheads, travel and subsistence and minor office equipment. His own research is externally funded and he receives no research support from NCAS.

27. Each of the centres has a specialist director or head and, in their own fields, they are internationally recognised experts who carry out research in their own right. These staff are university or analogue organisation employees and the host institution receives a financial contribution, individually negotiated, to compensate for the NCAS role. For ACMSU this is a 10% contribution, for DIAC and UWERN it is 50% and for the remainder it is 100%. The management group of NCAS consists of the Director, the Centre Directors/Heads and the Swindon Office Liaison Officer and meets quarterly. There is an NCAS Advisory Group of independent scientists that meets annually, with the NCAS Management Group, to review the scientific progress of NCAS and its plans for the following year. The membership consists of national and international academics, government department representatives, and senior Met Office and operational centre scientists.
28. NCAS has adopted a multi-faceted approach to achieve its mission. The SMA team was highly impressed with the outstanding leadership shown by the Director and his Centre Directors in giving a sense of purpose and cohesion to a previously disparate academic community, enabling it to produce, collectively, considerably more than the sum of its individual parts.
29. The Directors of the Centres input their contribution to strategy through quarterly management meetings. The input of NCAS staff to strategy discussions is mainly at the individual centre level at meetings with line managers and with the directors. **The SMA team emphasises the value of wide staff involvement in strategy development at all levels.**
30. NCAS seeks to ensure that the atmospheric science community has ample opportunity to meet for scientific exchange. Each of the three research themes; climate processes, small-scale processes and weather, and atmospheric composition has an annual conference. The largest of these attracts around 100 scientists. Every other year these annual conferences are co-located with the Royal Meteorological Society's Biennial Conference. NCAS also organises a number of workshops focused on different areas of atmospheric science.
31. NCAS has produced, in collaboration with other UK atmospheric scientists, the UK Atmospheric Science Strategy. This strategy matches the NERC priority areas of the Earth's life-support systems, climate change and sustainable economies. The SMA Team considered that NCAS contributed to the Climate Change priority in an exemplary fashion and that **the already significant contributions to the other two themes could, with advantage, be further extended.**

32. The quality and status of NCAS research in all three priority areas establishes NCAS as a major centre of expertise in the practical application of the Earth System Science approach. **The Team concluded that the NCAS centres had a significant role to play in the development of the UK Earth System Science capability in general.**

Term of Reference 3

To assess the effectiveness of arrangements to set research aims and objectives (including monitoring and data management objectives), monitor progress and evaluate output.

33. NCAS has an annual reporting system in which each centre submits a report to the Director that sets out the scientific and technical outcomes of the previous year, establishes goals for the following year and lists the publication details. The Director then reviews these reports and produces an overall NCAS report that is considered by the NCAS Advisory Group. The NCAS Management Group meets quarterly to monitor progress and outputs and provides a written summary of action points. The Director visits all the Centres on an informal basis while the day-to-day direction of the Centres is managed by the individual Directors/Heads.
34. Part of the process leads to the development and updating of the UK Atmospheric Science Strategy, which is developed in consultation with the whole UK research community. The Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology also provides feedback on its needs for atmospheric science research. Minutes and notes from all these meetings were shown to the SMA team and the organisation and record keeping was commended.
35. The SMA team was shown examples of Centre reports and the team was impressed with the ways employed to set aims and to monitor progress. The methods differ between the various centres, e.g., CGAM operates as a co-ordinating centre utilising a principally directed approach whereas UWERN tends towards a model that synthesises the ideas of its diverse community, while both operate as centres of excellence.
36. The Team was less clear on the utility of the ways currently used by NERC to evaluate the output of NCAS. **The Team felt that NCAS should consider metrics to measure output that reflected both the novel mode of collaborative science under which NCAS operates and also user expectations.** Nevertheless the team recognises that output evaluation can easily become a major resource consuming activity and should only be undertaken to the extent that it provides real added value in supporting and enhancing the research activity.
37. The evaluation of BADC's output is determined by the experience of the users of its database. The total number of registered users of BADC data is approximately 4900 and brief details of a user survey are given in paragraphs 71 and 72 below. There were many examples of real added-value and some indication of user requirements not being able to be met (see paragraph 71). A

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wider and better appreciation of the work of BADC was gained when a Science and Management Audit of the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) was undertaken in November 2004 – with some commonality of membership. BADC has around 300 – 400 active users and these users felt that its key strengths are the range and quantity of available data. The added value that BADC brought was clearly demonstrated to the team who also noted that BADC has addressed the comments from its users and considers BADC has effective arrangements in place to set its aims and objectives.

38. One area that was missing from current NCAS strategy was biology and deposition. The SMA team appreciated that some areas had of necessity been neglected when NCAS was launched because of the shortfall in available funding but felt that there was now a distinct need to develop the biological side of NCAS' work, in collaboration with other NERC Centres.

Term of Reference 4

To evaluate the achievements and productivity of the NCAS programme for scientific research, monitoring and data management activities and to grade the quality of the programme/s informed by previous evaluations and international benchmarks (evaluation based on NERC Assessment Criteria). QQR 3.15 vii

39. The NCAS I proposal set out the research and services/facilities programme to be delivered over the period of funding from 1 April 2002 to 31 March 2006. The proposal described three research headings: climate processes and change, hazardous weather and atmospheric composition. For climate processes and change the research and services are provided by CGAM and for chemistry-climate interactions by ACMSU. Hazardous weather research is conducted by UWERN and atmospheric composition research by DIAC. BADC is responsible for data stewardship (curation) and observational facilities by FAAM and UFAM.
40. Under this Term of Reference NCAS provided details of its publications: these average 26 p.a. for each research centre and 4 p.a. for each service facility. Further comment on publications is provided under ToR 7.
41. For ACMSU, CGAM and UWERN the main funding category is research and it was under this heading, in particular the directed programmes aspect, that evaluation was undertaken. For BADC the assessment was made under the services and facilities category, the main funding category for this Centre. The other centres and facilities were noted but not formally assessed by this SMA.

The following table summarises the science assessments and discussion on each Centre's activities is found below.

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	Excellence	Fit to NERC Priorities	Risk Reward	Value for Money
ACMSU	$\alpha 5$	A	4	V
BADC	$\alpha 4$	A	4	V
CGAM	$\alpha 5$	A	4	V
UWERN	$\alpha 4$	B	4	V

CGAM

42. CGAM has 12 separate science projects and the SMA team considered 7 of these in detail using the NERC Assessment Criteria. 5 of the 7 projects were considered to be producing science in the $\alpha 5$ category, namely science of exceptional merit, attracting comments such as original, highly distinctive and crossing boundaries. The science produced by the other projects was considered to be in the $\alpha 4$ category, with some aspects of project 4 (production of a dataset in conjunction with ECMWF) considered to be more a service or facility rather than innovative science, but which was nevertheless, producing high quality work. Overall therefore the SMA team considered that CGAM was producing science mainly in the highest, $\alpha 5$, category and it would expect this to have a major scientific impact internationally.

43. The SMA team considered that CGAM's science was a complete fit to NERC's highest science priorities as identified in *Science for a Sustainable Future*. The risk-reward category was considered to be "medium risk and high reward" namely category 4. The SMA team considered that CGAM was offering excellent value for money in that CGAM was extremely efficient in leveraging additional research funding over and above its NERC allocation and that this placed it in category V for value for money. Thus overall the SMA team rated CGAM science at: $\alpha 5$, A, 4 and V – **a rating in the excellent category.**

UWERN

44. The SMA team considered 6 of UWERN's 7 science themes, the seventh is work that is at an exploratory stage. Themes 1 to 4 all exhibited elements of $\alpha 5$ science and overall were offering science across the $\alpha 5/\alpha 4$ boundary. Theme 2 exhibited work with distinct $\alpha 5$ elements and theme 3 had taken boundary layer work to a high intellectual level and the SMA team saw this as distinct $\alpha 5$ science and looked forward to reading more of this work in publications. Themes 5 and 6 were seen as good enabling science. Theme 6 had identified a significant need and for both themes the SMA team felt there were synergies with each other that could be exploited. Overall the team felt that UWERN science was operating at the high $\alpha 4$ level.

45. The team considered the fit to NERC priorities was good although not absolute. To a large extent this is because UWERN activities cover a broad scientific area whereas the NERC priorities have a more specific application. Nevertheless, the Team considered that UWERN is significant in underpinning the NERC Science Strategy in this area. UWERN conducts its

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research in a medium risk and high reward fashion, i.e. 4 on the scale. Its cost effectiveness is extremely good by means of its links into the wider academic community and by operating in this fashion it exerts an impressive leverage; the team considered that UWERN merited a V in this area. Overall UWERN was rated at α 4, B, 4 and V – a rating in the excellent category.

ACMSU

46. The Centre has two aims; to carry out world-class research in atmospheric chemistry and atmospheric change and to support the UK atmospheric chemistry research community. The Centre focuses on global scale problems in the troposphere and stratosphere and the connection between atmospheric chemistry and climate change. ACMSU has achieved some notable success in using the Unified Model to investigate the role of meteorological variability, tropospheric forcing and sea surface temperature on ozone change at decadal timescales. Its current major orientation is the development, with the Met Office, of a coupled chemistry/climate model (UKCA) for predicting changes in atmospheric composition. The Centre has developed key models of atmospheric chemistry that are used by other organisations internationally. ACMSU is in turn supported by laboratory measurements and field studies made by these organisations.
47. The SMA team considered that ACMSU is a world-class centre both in the quality of its science and the way that it is communicating its results. The Team graded it α 5 without any hesitation. It saw the ACMSU team as real professionals and leaders in the field and saw its work as a flagship programme. It has a close fit to NERC strategy, corresponding to A on the scale. In terms of risk the SMA team noted that there is a risk of significant turnover of staff who might leave if a judgement on continued funding is made late in the funding cycle, consequently the team judged this work to be medium risk and high reward. It was felt that the ACMSU Director, Prof. Pyle, made a large contribution, which is predominantly funded by his university. Increasing the level of NCAS support to a larger fraction of his time will not only better serve Prof. Pyle and ACMSU but also allow for a leading scientist to take over this position if it became necessary in the future. Otherwise, a leading scientist may not be able to spend the necessary time to make ACMSU a success. In terms of cost-effectiveness the team judged ACMSU to be offering excellent value for money. In summary: ACMSU science was rated at α 5, A, 4 and V – a rating in the excellent category.

DIAC

48. Although DIAC was not formally assessed as part of the SMA, since the Institute was only formed in 2003, the SMA Team considered its research and service objectives essential for advancing understanding of air chemistry at surface level and impacts on health. Mike Pilling is the internationally renowned Director of the group and he receives funding from NCAS to carry out these duties, covering 50% of his time. This has enabled his teaching load to be substantially reduced. Like other NCAS Directors, his tremendous good will is essential to the future success of his Centre. The SMA Team was

concerned that the objectives for DIAC, which fully reflect the NCAS strategy, might not be fully supported by the funding available, currently 11% of NCAS total funding. In the Team's view there is a significant risk that DIAC will not be fully able to deliver its programme, given the funding level. Given this the team hesitated to suggest that DIAC might consider further work but it appeared to the team that DIAC could ideally undertake more urban, small-scale work as a starting point for illuminating links between environment and health.

49. DIAC is also adversely affected by the termination of the COSMAS programme. It needs the laboratory studies of basic chemical processes to continue in order to fulfil its objectives. The team suggested that as a first small step, if practicable there could be a redistribution of funding within NCAS and in the longer term DIAC needs a significant injection of money. The Team also suggested that DIAC rethink its priorities to shift some of its emphases.

50. BADC, UFAM and FAAM are discussed under ToR 8.

Term of Reference 5

To review the extent and productivity of national and international scientific links, including: the role NCAS plays in national leadership, cooperation and otherwise adding value by its existence; in developing international cooperation; for technology expensive projects; for coordinating distributed major programmes solving complex scientific problems; and for fostering a co-operative multidisciplinary approach. QQR 3.11 iii

51. NCAS aims to involve as much of the UK academic community as possible. Formally this is managed through the NCAS Affiliated Institutions. Affiliation involves an active participation in the strategic planning and execution of the atmospheric science research programme. The designation of NCAS Affiliated Institution is given to an academic-related organisation that supports atmospheric research and the invitation is directed at Vice-Chancellor level, with the lead (or deputy) person attending the annual meeting. Additionally NCAS distributes funds to 18 different universities. This model was designed to ensure that NCAS has links throughout the academic community nationally.

NCAS Affiliated Institutions

Academic Members	
University of Birmingham	University of Bristol
CCLRC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory	University of Cambridge
Cardiff University	University of Edinburgh
University of Essex	University of Hertfordshire
Heriot-Watt University	Imperial College, London
Lancaster University	University of Leeds
University of Leicester	University of Nottingham
University of Oxford	Queen Mary, University of London

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University of Reading	University of Salford
University of Southampton	University of Strathclyde
University of Surrey	University College, London
UMIST	University of East Anglia
University of Wales, Aberystwyth	University of York
NERC Research & Collaborative Members	
British Antarctic Survey	British Geological Survey
Centre for Ecology and Hydrology	Centre for Terrestrial Carbon Dynamics
Data Assimilation Research Centre	Environmental Systems Science Centre
Plymouth Marine Laboratory	Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Southampton Oceanography Centre	Tyndall Centre

52. NCAS has strong links to the Met Office, at a variety of different levels. Individual scientists within NCAS have well-established links with Met Office scientists and at a formal level there exists the Joint Centre for Mesoscale Meteorology (JCMM), which is a joint Met Office – University group established at the University of Reading. In the University of Reading there are 6 scientists from the Hadley Centre working with CGAM. It is planned to have a member of the Met Office working with ACMSU in the very near future. Other links with the Met Office are through projects such as UK Chemistry and Aerosols (UKCA), the Earth Simulator UK-Japan project, the UK-HiGEM project and, through FAAM, the joint activity involving the new aircraft.
53. There are 6-monthly meetings with the Met Office involving the Chief Scientist, the Director of the Hadley Centre and the Director of Numerical Weather Prediction and from NCAS, the Director, Director UWERN, Prof. B Hoskins, non-executive Director of the Met Office, and Dr A Kaye from the NERC Swindon Office. Prof. J Slingo is a member of the Met Office Scientific Advisory Committee and Dr S Mobbs was a member of the MoD Expert panel on Sustaining Scientific Excellence of the Met Office. Overall the SMA team considered that the joint working between the Met Office and NCAS was successfully supporting operational meteorology and climate change prediction with fundamental research.
54. In addition to the continued collaboration with the Hadley Centre noted above, the team considered that NCAS should seek to further develop existing collaborative links with other centres, for example with the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (CEH) with respect to biosphere/atmosphere interactions. The support of the UK universities' Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme, UGAMP, as a network of excellence, by CGAM and ACMSU is also an important community activity by NCAS.
55. The SMA Team judged that NCAS has been too modest about its achievements in strengthening the whole community. In particular it drew the following conclusions:
- **NCAS adds significant value in the areas of research in which it is a world leader.** It has made a good start and it is especially impressive that

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NCAS has successfully crossed boundaries between science areas; for example, its work in linking cloud-resolving modelling into the representation of clouds and their effects in climate, and the linkage between urban meteorology and urban chemistry.

- Notably NCAS has successfully brought together Affiliated Institutions outside the NCAS community and all have been involved in the development of the NCAS strategy. This also includes non-University institutions such as the Hadley Centre.
- NCAS was set up specifically to address a range of issues in a new and forceful manner and one excellent example is the new NERC FREE programme, which probably would not have happened under any other model.
- The team was unable to identify any other co-operative organisations in atmospheric science, in other countries, that function in the same way as NCAS. As far as the team is aware NCAS is uniquely successful in operating the Collaborative Centres model. The experience to date should be used as a resource for others and NCAS is in a strong position to further develop the operation of the model to support the science and the careers and prospects of the researchers involved.
- A key strength of the NCAS model is the formation of links with other agencies, nevertheless there is potential for more to be done in this area. ACMSU could collaborate more outside Cambridge and should strengthen its links with DIAC. **NCAS is encouraged to forge close ties with carbon cycle work that is being carried out elsewhere in the NERC community.** In particular the team discussed how NCAS would relate to the recently formed QUEST Programme and urged NCAS and QUEST to examine this relationship.

56. Many individual researchers within NCAS are internationally recognised leaders in their own fields. NCAS provided an impressive list of international links and success in obtaining EU Framework 6 funding. The SMA team felt it worth noting that NCAS is a world leader and adds significant value in the European and international arena and that the Directors of the individual Centres demonstrably lead on a number of European projects. Individuals from the NCAS community are already widely recognised as experts in Europe and internationally. The team felt that NCAS could usefully aim to be recognised, as its programme develops, as the focal institute of its individual researchers, much as the Hadley Centre is generally mentioned alongside any public contributions by its scientific staff. This would be of value the NCAS in maintaining its position as a national capability and resource as the staffing structure inevitably changes in the future.

57. Both supercomputing under CGAM and the FAAM aircraft are enabling major collaborative programmes addressing complex scientific problems. They are discussed more fully under ToR 8.

Term of Reference 6

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To assess NCAS's knowledge transfer of outputs, and take up by users, from research and monitoring programmes into new products and services, including data, information and advice (evaluation based on NERC Assessment Criteria).

58. NCAS has the following major customers and users: Met. Office including the Hadley Centre; other operational weather forecasting centres such as ECMWF; NERC Research and Collaborative Centres; UK Government Departments; the EU; the UK academic community that uses NCAS facilities and international agencies including WMO, IPCC, FAO and ICTP. **The SMA team was disappointed that there were relatively few stakeholders who commented on the relationship between themselves and NCAS.**
59. Much NCAS research is policy related with centres being involved in IPCC and WMO/UNEP assessments and work with DEFRA. FAST enables NCAS to communicate with government departments and vice versa. Currently NCAS knowledge transfer is driven by open literature and also particularly by the work of BADC. BADC has around 3000 users who are registered for access to restricted databases, of whom around 50% are non-NERC supported. Of BADC's 4900 registered users some 1600 are from overseas and 3000 are from outside the atmospheric science community. BADC has much to offer areas such as CLIVAR data management.
60. The SMA team recommended:
- That the Director continue in his efforts to improve one-to-one relationships with the Met Office and DEFRA.
 - **The NCAS brochure should be updated.** There is no one document or material that quickly and simply explains NCAS. This should be a priority of the NCAS science communications manager.

Term of Reference 7

To assess whether efficient, effective and economical use is being made of resources (including manpower, facilities, data and equipment) in order to successfully manage NCAS and examine the value for money of NCAS activities, including science, in comparison with other providers, where this would be practical. QQR 3.15 iv

61. NCAS funding has been synchronised to end on 31 March 2006 and the sum total of current funding is shown below.

NERC funding to NCAS over the period (in £M)

Total NCAS funding 2002 - 2006	01/02	02/03	03/04	04/05	05/06	Total 2002/2006
CGAM		0.77	1.17	1.61	1.85	5.40
ACMSU		0.24	0.26	0.28	0.30	1.08
UWERN (incl. Director)		0.45	0.50	0.50	0.75	2.20
DIAC (incl. Aber. Monitoring)		0.44	0.55	0.60	0.65	2.24
BADC (incl. metadata)		0.59	0.63	0.67	0.74	2.62
UFAM (incl. Chilbolton)		0.11	0.71	1.01	1.01	2.84
FAAM		0.10	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.60

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NCAS Directorate	0.17	0.18	0.20	0.23	0.78
Communications Manager	-	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.08
Small initiatives	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.20
Partnership Agreements (e.g. Met Office)	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.13	0.43
Capital Equipment Round 2004	-	-	0.25	-	0.25
Cambridge Readership	0.03	0.04	-	-	0.08
COSMAS	1.00	1.00	-	-	2.00
Total = NCAS I + additions 02/04	4.05	5.71	5.80	6.23	21.79

62. NCAS manages a High Performance Computing atmospheric science consortium to utilise national supercomputing facilities – the costs are held outside of NCAS funding and are currently at £1.13M p.a. NCAS provided figures on publications for the research-dominated Centres. The average cost per paper is £22k.

63. Staff issues were noted under this heading. Two significant issues arose with respect to staff; one was concern about contract work rather than permanent employment and the other was the career structure for support staff (normally in computation but also in instrumentation). The former issue is partly considered under this ToR and the latter under ToR 8 below, but both are more fully covered under change processes in ToR 10 below.

64. The SMA team found:

- NCAS does not have any responsibility for buildings and does not have any NERC employees, keeping the outlay and liability for NERC low.
- During the review it emerged that some staff were under the impression that March 2006 is a definite cut off date with a possible “cliff edge” finality of funding. They were not aware of the normal NERC policy of ramping down funding for collaborative centres. All collaborative centres should have received a letter explaining this. It is of vital importance when maintaining the careers of post-docs. **This information needs to be conveyed to NCAS staff, as a contingency measure.**
- Post-docs are recruited on the basis of what they can contribute to NCAS rather than purely to encourage strategic links or their careers. The links between ACMSU and DIAC need to be strengthened and there is a meeting planned for the Director of ACMSU to meet the Head of the host department for DIAC in Leeds.

65. The SMA Team concluded that NCAS offered extraordinarily good value for money because it is supported and subsidised so much by the university sector (Mike Pilling for example) and NERC does not have to pay for the infrastructure. This matches exactly to the NERC criterion of excellence in value for money, which is: *Excellent value for money. Possibly some of the full cost of the research borne elsewhere in external finances, or in-kind input.*

66. The Team found:

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- The "added value" and "net effect" of NCAS as reviewed by the panel presents a considerable return on the initial investment, **which is arguably one of the key achievements of NCAS.**
- **Extremely good value for money is demonstrated** when examining output in comparison to input from a suite of Directors most of whom are not employed full time by NCAS.
- NCAS has successfully realised new funding opportunities.

Term of Reference 8

To assess whether NCAS effectively invests in the development and support of major capital equipment, facilities, services and support staff. QQR 3.11 viii

67. This ToR will primarily consider capital equipment but will also consider BADC as an element as well as the issue of support staff.
68. The UK atmospheric science community had acquired several major pieces of capital equipment prior to the establishment of NCAS through programmes such as ACSOE, IFMA and COSMAS. Through Joint Infrastructure Funding (JIF) NCAS has established a set of ground-based instruments that form the core of UFAM, and also through JIF the joint Met Office-NERC research aircraft. NCAS has made few capital investments so far but is about to make two that are financially significant. One is an instrument to measure NO_xy and the other is the development of a Big Data Analysis Network (BDAN).

BADC

69. BADC will implement BDAN to manage storage at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, at Daresbury Laboratory, at Manchester and at Reading. The SMA team was presented with details of the various hardware elements that will contribute to BDAN and the net effect of the system will be to empower users to exploit fully the non-linearity of high-resolution simulations of the atmosphere. Many other users will have their access considerably enhanced.
70. The team was impressed overall with BADC. It is responsive to NCAS needs whilst also providing service to the wider community. There seemed to be some tension between Core and Responsive model funding. Resources had to be diverted from Core to deal with responsive model work with the difference being made up later. However, the team felt confident in BADC's ability to manage that. Some of its broader function, responding to needs of researchers for data, was clearly complementary to the role of the Met Office. The team was particularly impressed by the "cutting edge" work on e-science and the grid, and the fact that BADC also managed some research effort. BADC had also addressed the criticism in their 2000 SMA of not doing enough on data archaeology.
71. BADC conducted a survey of its registered users in April/May 2004 – a brief summary is:

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Strengths	Weaknesses
Range & quality of data	Access restrictions
Fast network	Lack of tools
Prompt human response	Update frequency

72. The BADC comment on this survey is “Much work underway to address these, but none are easy to deal with!” However, since the response rate was 7% the conclusions should be viewed with caution.

73. BADC has an additional commitment to provide services for users outside the NCAS community and in the longer run this might prove to be a significant, fixed and possibly increasing cost within a finite NCAS budget. Consequently the SMA team was concerned that funding of BADC is currently solely through NCAS and might need enhancing directly from NERC.

74. The SMA team considered the BADC science under the category of shared services and facilities and assessed the performance thus:

Excellence – excellent – delivering a significant national capability - α4.

Fit – completely aligned to NERC priorities – A.

Risk/reward – a discernible operational risk and a high reward – 4.

Cost Effectiveness – offering excellent value for money – V.

In summary: **BADC was rated in the excellent category.**

75. Both UFAM and FAAM are managed by NCAS. Neither was formally assessed by the SMA but presentations were made to the team and some operational issues raised.

FAAM

76. FAAM’s remit is to provide an airborne atmospheric measurement capability for the NERC/Met Office research communities, specifically:

- Coordination of planning of measurement campaigns,
- Provision of core instruments and operators,
- Provision of quality controlled core data to the users/BADC,
- Maintaining and updating the core instrument suite,
- Advise on design/fitting of new instrumentation,
- Facilitating installation of new scientific equipment,
- Arranging appropriate training for aircraft users.

77. A total of 65 instruments is soon to be available, including 24 core and 6 potential core, the remainder will be available through collaboration or other arrangement with University/ Met Office groups. The SMA team endorsed the quality of this facility.

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78. Managing the selection and scheduling of projects is a particularly complex, long-term task for which NCAS and the Met. Office have established a comprehensive planning procedure. The agreement with BAES involves using the aircraft for an agreed minimum number of flying hours per annum for the 10-year period of the current contract. The flying program for the first 2-3 years is now well established. However, the flying program for the later period of the contract is not currently defined, giving flexibility for the science programs of the Met Office and NERC. The Operations Committee has responsibility for providing advice on the detailed flying program to the Head of FAAM. Outline project proposals are submitted to FAAM, who advise on the technical feasibility (not the science). In practice, FAAM assists in making sure proposals are technically feasible wherever possible. Those proposals that are technically feasible then enter the NERC peer review process. The successful ones are then allocated a suitable flying slot by the Operations Committee/Head of FAAM. For NCAS core-funded research, FAAM is approached directly with the requirements and, if feasible, they would then be allocated a suitable flying slot by the Operations Committee/Head of FAAM.
79. In the course of the SMA presentations the Team heard from a number of NCAS project proposers who already had core funding for FAAM projects but who were uncertain about how their projects would proceed. It appeared that in some cases, proposers felt that their projects might be jeopardised if this uncertainty over the allocation of flying-time, persisted. **The SMA Team recommends that the NCAS Director and the Head of FAAM investigate these concerns with all project proposers to determine if there are problems associated with the long time scales and flexibility requirements and, if so, whether they can be minimised and the process of allocation be effectively communicated across the NCAS community.**

UFAM

80. UFAM provides ground-based and airborne instruments and expertise for their development and utilization. It is a distributed set of centres of expertise (CoE) in atmospheric instrumentation at various UK universities. There are Instrument Scientists at each institution.
81. UFAM was initiated in 2001 as a result of a successful proposal to the Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF). UFAM has provided the infrastructure for many collaborative field campaigns which address major issues central to NCAS (e.g. NAMBLEX, TORCH, CSIP, ITOP). UFAM provides specialised ground-based and airborne instruments and expertise for their development and utilization. Instruments and Instrument Scientists are located at Centres of Excellence where they maintain and operate instruments and make them available to the broader community and ensure quality of data.
82. The SMA Team was impressed by this facility but did express concern that as the instruments were located in a variety of different institutions there was a risk that as scientists moved then either the instruments might move with them and be possibly lost to NCAS or that the instruments may remain in a university without the expertise to operate them. The current situation with

one scientist associated with each instrument contributes to the high cost of the facility. This might be improved in the future with each scientist taking charge of more than one instrument.

Supercomputing

83. The SMA Team received an impressive presentation from the Computational Science Group. This group provides computing services throughout NCAS. It answers queries, runs training courses particularly on the Unified Model, and provides and develops tools to exploit the NCAS database. The cost of computing throughout NCAS is estimated to be £1.13M in 2004 with a further £28k on HPCX. The main concerns that the Team had after this presentation centred on the allocation of supercomputing time by NERC in that NCAS does not know how much time it will be allocated sufficiently far in advance to allow proper long-term planning of the resources.

Term of Reference 9

To assess the extent to which the NCAS Science Programmes and core mission are supported and enhanced by external funding as an indication of the need by the user community for the research, monitoring and data management functions. To form a view as to the risks inherent in the balance of funding within NCAS and the advantages and disadvantages of the income portfolio.

84. NCAS has received an average of £3.17M p.a. external funding over the period 2002 to 2005, taking into account funding that has been committed, and this compares with an average NCAS core funding of £5.4M p.a. Thus external funding amounts to a further 59% of NCAS funding. The research centres (ACMSU, CGAM, DIAC and UWERN) have attracted some 116% of external funding when compared with their core NCAS allocation.

85. The Team was impressed with the amount of leverage that NCAS has been able to obtain but was concerned that although the financial risk to NCAS was low there was a significant risk that if core funding remains relatively low then NCAS may not achieve its mission. There was concern that it is hard for new science to break into established NERC patterns of funding. The SMA Team concluded that it is also important to look at the balance of funding across NERC activities rather than simply look at the input of external funding. It was noted that NCAS was founded at a low point in the NERC funding cycle and **the Team recommends that a significant financial uplift is given to NCAS in the next funding round.**

Term of Reference 10

To assess whether NCAS has internal processes of change and rejuvenation ensuring that programmes of work are brought to an end when needed. This includes assessing if NCAS enables a good flow of new ideas and people, including scrutiny of the processes in universities for long-term career development of staff employed with NCAS funding. QQR 3.15 viii

86. NCAS is an outward looking organisation and staff are managed such that they have expectations that they may be redeployed onto new activities as

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priorities change. A similarly flexible approach is made to the deployment of financial resources and an example of this is the setting up of NCAS when only £10M was available instead of the £21.6M that the science portfolio had requested. Other examples were provided to the Team of scientific and leadership change within NCAS.

87. NCAS has 12 studentships across the UK, which allows for new PIs to be involved with NCAS research. It helps train the next generation of atmospheric scientists and allows the involvement of NCAS research staff in the supervision of students and contributes to both students' and staff career development.
88. Career development was a major area of interest for the SMA Team, particularly as NERC funding is frequently of a short-term nature. NCAS has yet to resolve this issue, which is by no means unique to NCAS. NCAS views on career development may not match those of the host university and most NCAS staff are on fixed-term contracts (except BADC and some at FAAM). At a senior level the situation is less problematic but at junior level it is of serious concern. There are ongoing discussions between NCAS and NERC as to how the situation may be alleviated and examples were discussed at the review.
89. A further staff issue arises with the various categories of staff employed within NCAS. Each university has different terms and conditions and comparability across NCAS is extremely difficult. A national agreement has recently been concluded and this should help NCAS staff to feel they have equal opportunities for recognition, status and promotion although there remains a disparity in conditions between academic and "support" staff. It was noted that NCAS is at an early stage in its development and this area may need more time to be fully assessed. It was noted that there is a good flow of new ideas and people, which is an advantage of the dispersed system in a university environment. **However the SMA Team did feel that long-term development of staff employed is the point of greatest risk in NCAS.** The NCAS Director himself wants to keep a few (about 6) longer-term / permanent contracts for staff and postdocs in order to maintain a long-term skills base and the Team fully supports him in this objective. This would use NERC funding to help to persuade and support universities to build capability. **The difficulty lies in NERC persuading individuals and universities that NCAS has a long-term existence.** The publication of NERC Council 04/56, which states that NCAS is an "Established Centre" and not time-limited should redress concerns in this area. It was considered that making available resources for re-tooling and re-directing people to maximise the opportunities for flexible re-deployment could contribute to improved career prospects.

Term of Reference 11

To consider the appropriateness of the duration of funding for all areas of activity in NCAS and the frequency with which funds should be sought from NERC.

90. NCAS was initially funded for four years from 1 April 2002 to 31 March 2006; the normal five-year period was changed to accommodate a funding

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disparity between the original request of £21.6M for five years and the amount available of £10M for four years. The NCAS II Proposal is to be submitted to NERC by 31 October 2004 and this will be for five year funding to 31 March 2011.

91. After lengthy discussion centred around the NERC criteria guide of the nature and state of development of the scientific field, **the SMA Team felt that the duration of funding should be five years. The Team is aware that this outcome is not ideal for supporting expertise in this field through the management and provision of career opportunities. If the maintenance of expertise and provision of career opportunities had been the major thrust of this Term of Reference then a longer funding cycle would have been recommended.**

92. **The SMA Team thought that the next tranche of funding should be reviewed in year 3.** This would ameliorate any "cliff-edge" aspect to the last year of funding and allow sensible planning of resources and staff in the event of a significant change in NERC-NCAS strategy

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Acknowledgements

The Team acknowledges the help in the SMA it received from the various members of NCAS who put together the list of documents and those who helped in both Cambridge and Reading. A particular mention is given to the members of NCAS who travelled considerable distances to give their presentations.

The Secretariat would also like to acknowledge the help given by the SMA Team members throughout the review.

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ToR	Summary of Findings & Recommendations (Bold)	Paragraph
1	NCAS is an important national capability.	17, 20
1	NCAS may not have adequate resources to fulfil its remit.	18
1	The connection between NCAS and government, in its widest aspect, could be strengthened.	23
1	Effort should be put into re-invigorating FAST.	24
1	There would be benefits to all concerned with increased collaboration between NCAS and the Tyndall Centre and CEH	25
2	NCAS contribution to other areas of NERC strategy could be further extended	31
2	NCAS Centres have a significant role to play in the development of UK Earth System Science	32
3	NCAS should consider further ways to evaluate output.	36
4,8	NCAS science, as presented, was considered in the excellent category	43, 45, 47 & 74
4	There is a significant risk that DIAC will not be able to fully deliver its programme because of insufficient funding.	48
4	NCAS should redistribute funding, where practicable, to direct a greater fraction to DIAC. DIAC should reconsider its priorities and give more emphasis to laboratory measurements.	49
5	NCAS needs to forge close links with the carbon cycle research across NERC and in QUEST in particular.	55
6	The NCAS brochure should be updated.	60
7	NCAS staff need to be made aware of the NERC funding process.	64
7	NCAS demonstrates extremely good value for money	66
8	NCAS should investigate concerns over FAAM funding proposals and communicate the process to the NCAS community.	79
9	A significant financial uplift is given to NCAS in the next funding round.	85
10	NCAS should investigate the possibility of offering some staff permanent employment terms.	89
11	NCAS duration of funding should be five years.	91
11	The next tranche of funding should be reviewed in year 3	92

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Annex 1

Terms of Reference for NCAS Science & Management Audit

- 1 To assess whether NCAS provides a national capability and source of advice to Government. QQR 3.12 i
- 2 To assess the effectiveness of the scientific and management leadership and process for cultivating long-term vision/mission and strategy, and the contribution of NCAS towards NERC's Mission and 5-year Strategy. QQR 3.11 iv
- 3 To assess the effectiveness of arrangements to set research aims and objectives (including monitoring and data management objectives), monitor progress and evaluate output.
- 4 To evaluate the achievements and productivity of the NCAS programme for scientific research, monitoring and data management activities and to grade the quality of the programme/s informed by previous evaluations and international benchmarks (evaluation based on NERC Assessment Criteria). QQR 3.15 vii
- 5 To review the extent and productivity of national and international scientific links, including: the role NCAS plays in national leadership, cooperation and otherwise adding value by its existence; in developing international cooperation; for technology expensive projects; for coordinating distributed major programmes solving complex scientific problems; and for fostering a co-operative multidisciplinary approach. QQR 3.11 iii
- 6 To assess NCAS's knowledge transfer of outputs, and take up by users, from research and monitoring programmes into new products and services, including data, information and advice (evaluation based on NERC Assessment Criteria).
- 7 To assess whether efficient, effective and economical use is being made of resources (including manpower, facilities, data and equipment) in order to successfully manage NCAS and examine the value for money of NCAS activities, including science, in comparison with other providers, where this would be practical. QQR 3.15 iv
- 8 To assess whether NCAS effectively invests in the development and support of major capital equipment, facilities, services and support staff. QQR 3.11 viii
- 9 To assess the extent to which the NCAS Science Programmes and core mission are supported and enhanced by external funding as an indication of the need by the user community for the research, monitoring and data management functions. To form a view as to the risks inherent in the balance of funding within NCAS and the advantages and disadvantages of the income portfolio.
- 10 To assess whether NCAS has internal processes of change and rejuvenation ensuring that programmes of work are brought to an end when needed. This includes assessing if NCAS enables a good flow of new ideas and people, including scrutiny of the processes in universities for long-term career development of staff employed with NCAS funding. QQR 3.15 viii
- 11 To consider the appropriateness of the duration of funding for all areas of activity in NCAS and the frequency with which funds should be sought from NERC.

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Annex 2

Membership

The Team consisted of:

Alan Apling

Ex Head of Science and Technology Policy, Dept for Transport, recently retired, Chairman of the SMA Team,

Oystein Hov

Director of Research at the Norwegian Met Service and a member of NERC's Science and Innovation Strategy Board,

Huw Davies

Professor of Meteorology at ETH Zurich and Chairman of the NCAS Advisory Group,

Jo Haigh

Professor of Atmospheric Physics at Imperial College,

David Andrews

Professor of Atmospheric Dynamics at University of Oxford.

This group remained at Reading for the SMA and reviewed CGAM and UWERN additionally the Team received a presentation on UFAM. The remainder travelled to Cambridge to review ACMSU and BADC as well as receive presentations on DIAC and FAAM.

This group consisted of:

Akkihebbal Ravishankara

Senior Scientist at NOAA Aeronomy Lab, Boulder, Chairman in Cambridge,

Mike Ashfold

Professor of Chemistry at University of Bristol,

Roland Kallenborn

Senior Scientist at the Norwegian Institute for Air Research,

Jean-Pierre Pommereau

Atmospheric Chemist at CNRS Paris.

For BADC the Team included Howard Cattle Director of the International CLIVAR Project Office.

The Secretariat consisted of:

Jim Clipson

Lynne Porter

Liz Humphreys

Dr. Lorraine Plant

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Annex 3

Timetable

**NCAS SMA Visit
13 – 16 September 2004**

Monday 13 September: Meet at 1630 – SMA brief followed by NCAS Overview (A Thorpe), SMA team dinner and overnight in Reading

Tuesday 14 September:

0810 - Group B depart for Cambridge (Dept of Chemistry)

0915 - Group A depart for Reading University (A Thorpe at Cambridge)

Group A: Reading		Group B: Cambridge	
10.00 – 10.45	CGAM overview (J Slingo)	On arrival	Coffee
10.45 – 11.00	SMA team discussion	10.45 – 11.15	ACMSU overview (J Pyle)
11.00 - 11.30	Coffee	11.15 - 11.30	SMA team discussion
11.30 - 12.15	CGAM research staff and students	11.30 - 12.15	ACMSU PIs/students
12.15 – 12.30	SMA team discussion	12.15 – 12.30	SMA team discussion
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch	12.30 - 13.30	Lunch
13.30 - 14.00	Computational Support (Lois Steenman-Clark)	13.30 – 15.00	Tour of labs (A Cox)
14.00 – 14.15	SMA team discussion		
14.15 – 15.00	UGAMP/Reading PIs		
15.00 – 15.15	SMA team discussion	15.00 – 15.30	Tea
15.15 – 15.45	Tea	15.30 – 16.15	DIAC progress report (M Pilling)
15.45 – 16.30	UWERN overview (P Mason)	16.15 – 16.30	SMA team discussion
16.30- 16.45	SMA team discussion	16.30 – 17.00	Science Communications (L Watts)
Dinner incl: J Slingo, P Mason, A Blyth, C Collier, L Steenman-Clark, S Belcher, R Plant		Dinner incl: J Pyle, A Cox, M Pilling, B Lawrence, R Jones, L Watts	

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Wednesday 15 September: (A Thorpe at Reading)

Reading		Cambridge	
9.30 - 10.15	UWERN projects (S Belcher, C Collier)	9.30 - 10.15	BADC (B Lawrence)
10.15 - 10.30	SMA team discussion	10.15 - 10.30	SMA team discussion
10.30 - 11.00	Met Office collaboration	10.30 -11.15	FAAM progress report (R Jones)
11.00 - 11.15	SMA team discussion	11.15 - 11.30	SMA team discussion
11.15 - 11.45	Coffee	11.30 - 12.30	Lunch
11.45 - 12.30	UWERN projects (S Mobbs, R Plant)	12.30	Depart for Reading
12.30 - 12.45	SMA team discussion		
12.45 - 13.45	Lunch		
13.45 - 14.30	UFAM (A Blyth)		
14.30 - 14.45	SMA team discussion		
15.00 - 17.30	SMA team discuss report		
Dinner at Reading			

Thursday 16 September:

09.00 - 10.00 Feedback to Director of NCAS, by SMA chairman, on outcome of visit.

End of SMA visit

Annex 4

Organisation Diagram

